

ISic2989

I.Sicily inscription 2989

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Kate Jeremy,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [d(is)m(anibus)s(acrum)]
2. [---]ianus Aug(usti)
3. [lib(ertus)] tabul(arius) vixit an
4. [n]is XXII mensib(us) II
5. dieb(us) XI uxor et
6. [fr]a,t,ꝛes [pii]ssimo
7. [---]

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004 no. 38

Translation (en)

To the spirits of the departed, Julianus, freedman of the Emperor and archivist, lived for twenty-two years, two months and eleven days. His wife and brothers (set this up) to the most dutiful man.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175848

EDR 073194

EDCS 16100301

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1933.0028

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 38

Libertini, G 1931. Miscellanea epigrafica. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*. 27: 39-53. At 47 = Libertini (1981) 97

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 38 n.180

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